

SPQR

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org

Table of content

Visual Tools

Logo

Colors

Typography

Mockups

Logo

Main version

SPQR
Secure Post Quantum eRa

Logo

Secondary versions

Colors

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or grey.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors.

French Plum Primary

#730458

R115 G4 B88

C0 M97 Y24 K55

Jasper Orange Secondary

#E58951

R229 G137 B81

C0 M40 Y65 K10

Imperial Purple Secondary

#4C0141

R76 G1 B65

C0 M99 Y15 K70

White Neutral

#FFFFFF

R255 G255 B255

C0 M0 Y0 K0

Dark Grey Neutral

#515151

R81 G81 B81

C0 M0 Y0 K68

Schiaparelli Pink Accent

#E2006B

R226 G0 B107

C0 M100 Y53 K11

Colors

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (grey or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

Gradient table

100%	100%	100%	100%
------	------	------	------

80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

Aa

Titles

Cairo Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789
[(@#%\$^&)]"<>!?

Typography

Paragraph

The font displayed on the page is intended for use in paragraphs only.

Aa Bb

Cairo Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]"<>!?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation.

Mockups

SPQR

Secure Post Quantum eRa

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue duis dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue duis dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim.

SPQR

Brand Guidelines

